

Research Article

Addressing Malnutrition among Rural and Urban Households Using Bio-Fortified Cassava (Pro-Vitamin A Cassava): A Review¹Ajayi, A.J, ²Adeeko, A*, ²Bifarin, J.O, ³Umunna M. O and ⁴Elemasho, M.K¹Department of Crop Production, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure. Ondo State.²Department of Agricultural Extension and Management,
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Abstract

The paper reviewed the potentials of consuming bio-fortified cassava among rural and urban households in Nigeria. It explained the concept, prospect, health, nutritional benefits and opportunities presented by bio-fortification of cassava. Bio-fortification is the process of increasing the bio-available micronutrient density of staple crops through conventional plant breeding and modern biotechnology to achieve a measurable and positive impact on human health. The prospect of bio-fortification through biotechnology provides the nation with ample opportunities to alleviate food and nutrition insecurity, as well as create jobs for a new crop of researchers. Bio-fortified staple foods can contribute to body stores of iron, zinc, and vitamin A throughout the lifecycle, including those of children, adolescents, adult women, men, and the elderly. Micronutrients are required in the diet in small amounts but deficiencies can result in serious health consequences. Bio-fortification provides micronutrients which are essential for human health and nutrition and can also significantly contribute to reduce morbidity, malnutrition and mortality. The study concluded that bio-fortified cassava has the potential to improve the nutrition and health status of rural and urban households which can contribute to household productivity and improve the overall Gross Domestic Products (GDP) of Nigeria. The study recommended that more awareness on the nutritional benefits of bio-fortified cassava should be intensified and all stakeholders in the government and non-governmental area should be saddled with the responsibility of promoting the consumption of bio-fortified cassava.

Keywords: Bio-fortification, Bio-fortified cassava, Pro-vitamin A Cassava, Malnutrition, Rural and Urban Household

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Introduction

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* crantz), a major starch staple in Africa is particularly important in Nigeria and account for about 40% of cassava production in Africa (Egesi *et al.*, 2011). Cassava is one of the most important sources of energy in diet of African (Okogbenin *et al.*, 2011). Cassava, a crop that can withstand diseases, drought and pest is very rustic and can grow well under marginal environment where most annual crops would not survive (Okogbenin *et al.*, 2011). It grows on poor marginal soil and thus cultivated and eaten where both poverty and malnutrition is widespread. The crop is widely grown in the country and it provides household food security as well as means of economic empowerment to many poor -resource farmers (Egesi *et al.*, 2011). The crop is a source of calories for about 80 million Nigerians (Egesi *et al.*, 2011) and the per capita consumption of cassava in Nigeria is averaged at 226.93 gram/person/day with range of 131.16 gram/person/day in the dry savannah to 284.42 gram/person/day in humid forest zone (Philip *et al.*, 2005).

Although cassava has been identified as an energy rich crop, it contains very low levels of proteins, vitamins and minerals. Sayre *et al* (2011) reported that a typical cassava-based diet provides less than 30% of the minimum daily requirement for protein and only 10%-20% of that for iron, zinc, and vitamin A. The body obtains vitamin A in two ways. One is by manufacturing it from carotene, a vitamin precursor found in such vegetables as carrots, broccoli, squash, spinach and sweet potatoes. Vitamin A is not present in plant, but many vegetables and fruits contain one or more of a class of pigments that can be converted to vitamin A in the body; of these pigments, beta-carotene (pro-vitamin A) is an excellent source of vitamin activity (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2010). Vitamin A is required by human in very small amounts; the recommended intakes for adult men and women are 1000 and 800 micrograms, respectively. It is assumed that every 6 µg of beta-carotene has the activity of 1 µg of vitamin A (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2010). The other way the body obtain vitamin A is by absorbing ready-made vitamin A from plant eating organisms. Vitamin A can be obtained from animal sources as found in milk, cheese, egg yolk, liver and fresh-liver oil. Sufficient amount of vitamin A can be obtained in normal balanced diet. However, balanced diet is far from the reach of the poor which constitute a bulk of Nigerian populace. The foods within the reach of this category of people are usually cheap energy sources that are lacking in essential proteins and vitamins.

Vitamin A is an essential nutrient lacking in the diet of malnourished population. Vitamin A is a pale yellow primary alcohol derived from carotene. It affects the formation and maintenance of skin, mucous membranes, bones, and teeth; vision and reproduction. An early deficiency symptom is night blindness. Deficiency of micro-nutrient is wide spread especially vitamin A. Strategies at reducing the deficiency A include supplementation, diversifying diet and commercial fortification. The cost of these strategies is not within the reach of the poor. Commercial fortification was adopted some years back where certain household food materials such as sugar were fortified with vitamin A. The most recent strategy adopted in combating vitamin A deficiency is the use of “bio-fortification”.

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Ordinary food fortification refers to addition of supplements to food during processing to make it more nutritious whereas bio-fortification involves the development of crops that produce these micronutrients while they are growing. The novel process of bio-fortification of cassava applies conventional breeding which led to accumulation of coloured pro-vitamin A carotenoids in storage root. Carotenoids are auxillary photosynthesis pigments. According to Welsch, *et al.* (2010), allelic polymorphism is capable of enhancing flux of carbon through carotenogenesis and result in accumulation of coloured pro-vitamin A carotenoids in storage root. The single nucleotide polymorphism is present only in yellow-rooted/fleshed cultivars of cassava which have high carotenoids.

Cassava as an important staple food for millions of people around the world, especially among poorer communities in Africa and Latin America where many of the poor in these regions also suffer from vitamin A deficiency became a tool for correcting micronutrient deficiencies. Cassava with higher levels of pro-vitamin A can help reduce vitamin A deficiency among undernourished communities that rely upon cassava for sustenance. Therefore, consumption of cassava bio-fortified with pro-vitamin A (converted in the body to vitamin A) will have a significant positive impact on nutrition and overall health, especially among poorer communities. The objectives of this review are to explain the concept of bio-fortification of crops, the prospect of bio-fortification of cassava, the health and nutrition benefits of bio-fortification of cassavas and opportunities presented by bio-fortification of cassava.

The Pro-vitamin A Cassava

Research efforts of scientist at addressing the malnutrition and hidden hunger has resulted in the development of new varieties of cassava that are rich in Vitamin A. Among the partners involved in the development of this novel crop varieties are International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), International Centre for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), National Root Crop Research Institute (NRCRI) Umudike and Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (EMBRAPA). According to IITA, (2012), three pro-vitamin A cassava were released in December, 2011. The varieties were IITA genotypes, TMS 01/1368, TMS 01/1412, and TMS 01/1371. These varieties are suitable for food such as garri, fufu and high quality cassava flour (HQCF) and would change the nutritional status of poor people living on cassava based food. Efforts are geared towards multiplication of the stem cuttings of the newly released varieties for distribution to farming households.

Concept of Bio-fortification of Cassava

Bio-fortification can be described as a complementary, rural-targeted micronutrient program strategy for better reaching remote regions, which often comprise the majority of the malnourished vulnerable populations. Also bio-fortification is the process of increasing the bio-available micronutrient density of staple crops through conventional plant breeding and modern biotechnology to achieve a measurable and positive impact on human health. There are marked differences between traditional plant breeding and crop bio-fortification (Nestel *et al.*, 2006). Traditional breeding focuses on improving traits of known economic value and developing product

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concepts for existing markets. Traits are targeted for selection based on whether they can provide better crop and/or utilization options to farmers, but nutritional value as a trait for selection has been largely ignored.

Bio-fortification breeding, on the other hand, seeks to make an impact on human micronutrient status, an endeavor that entails merging breeding with nutrition and socio economics research to enhance traits that have measurable value in health outcomes. Bio-fortification breeding accesses the information it needs to identify such traits by linking directly to the human health and nutrition sectors (Nestel *et al.*, 2006), which have become an integral part of crop improvement and product concept development. At die core of any bio-fortification breeding program is a product pathway driven by potential impacts of research and nutrition. Collaboration between plant breeding and socioeconomics allows the exchange of information to identify target populations that consume target crops based on their micronutrient burden. The micronutrient burden is the burden imposed on individuals by micronutrient deficiencies and related diseases; it can be quantified using the Disability-Adjusted Life-Years (DALYs) approach (Stein *et al.*, 2005).

Measuring the effectiveness of bio-fortified crops in improving human health provides a benchmark for quantifying the ultimate success of bio-fortification as a cost effective public health intervention. For bio-fortification to be successful, micronutrient levels targeted by breeding programs must be derived from nutrition goals set by nutritionists who understand the complexities of making a measurable impact on human health. To set target levels and determine the likely contribution to nutritional status, critical information is needed on the bioconversion bioavailability of ingested nutrients; retention of the micronutrient after storage, processing, and cooking; human micronutrient requirements; and potential levels of consumption by the target population.

Genotypic differences in retention, post-harvest micronutrient deterioration, and concentrations of anti nutrients and promoters that inhibit or enhance micronutrient bioavailability have been established. Throughout crop development, nutrition and food technology are engaged in assessing the magnitude of genetic variation and genotypic differences for these traits; this allows breeders to increase bioavailability and determine the effect of micronutrient- dense crops or candidate varieties on micronutrient status via human efficacy trials (Stein *et al.*, 2005).

Prospect of Bio-fortification of Cassava

The prospect of bio-fortification through biotechnology provides the nation with ample opportunities to alleviate food and nutrition insecurity, as well as create new jobs for a new crop of researchers. The benefits that will accrue to farmers and processors likewise cannot be easily quantified. Consumption of bio-fortified foods will help in raising a young healthy population with a cognitive skills and development that can compete in a world driven by science and technology. The result will be increased productivity and quality of life of young Nigerians.

Malnutrition

According to Luchuo *et al* (2013), malnutrition is estimated to contribute to more than one third of all child deaths, although it is rarely listed as the direct cause (World Food Programme, 2000). Malnutrition literally means “bad nutrition” and technically includes both over- and under-nutrition. The World Food Programme (World Food Programme, 2000) defined malnutrition as “a state in which the physical function of an individual is impaired to the point where he or she can no longer maintain adequate bodily performance process such as growth, pregnancy, lactation, physical work and resisting and recovering from disease” (World Food Programme, 2000). Contributing to more than half of deaths in children worldwide; child malnutrition was associated with 54% of deaths in children in developing countries in 2001

Poverty is closely associated with malnutrition. One billion people who live in extreme poverty generally also consume fewer than their minimum requirements of 2100 calories per day (FAO/IFPRI, 2008). Poverty translates into insufficient access to food, in both quantity and quality, due to cash constraints as well as difficulties to access natural resources to produce this food, such as land or water. The present crisis constitutes an aggravating factor for poor households, rather than the only determinant of their food insecurity. Health infections further compound the situation as diseases such as malaria or persistent diarrhea can prevent absorption of adequate food and/or nutrients and contribute to poverty through labour loss and health and care costs. Likewise, living in poverty greatly increases susceptibility to poor health, as low income people often cannot access preventive health services, live in unhealthy environments and have limited access to adequate information.

Broader factors such as political, economic and agricultural also determine the current food crisis. The lack of investment in agriculture in the past 20 years, prompted by low food prices, as well as insufficient agricultural productivity and diversity, contributed to make some countries dependent on overseas’ imports and food aid, and thereby vulnerable to any increase of world food prices. It also resulted in a reduced diversity of foods consumed and is thereby an indirect cause of prevailing micronutrient deficiencies.

The complexity of the issue therefore requires an integrated response at all levels. In order to establish well targeted and sustainable policies, it is essential to identify the most vulnerable households, particularly in countries where inequalities of income are high, and where major geographic disparities exist. Since constraints and opportunities will depend on people’s livelihoods and socio-economic environment, vulnerable households should be clustered according to livelihoods, and a rapid analysis of coping mechanisms and causes of malnutrition should be carried out for each group.

The causes of malnutrition are classically clustered into food, health and care constraints. Specific problems such as inefficient health systems or high prevalence of infectious diseases will need to be addressed alongside agricultural issues through multidisciplinary groups.

As far as agriculture is concerned, more resilient food systems need to be promoted. The present commodity based market and export-oriented “value chain” approach needs to be complemented by integrated and risk adverse local approaches based on the sustainable management of natural resources and retrieval of relevant indigenous knowledge and culture. Such approaches would privilege local production, including production of staples, and year-round supply of local markets.

Health and Nutritional Benefits of Bio-fortification of Cassava

Bio-fortified staple foods can contribute to body stores of iron, zinc, and vitamin A throughout the lifecycle, including those of children, adolescents, adult women, men, and the elderly. The potential benefits from bio-fortification are, however, not equivalent across all of these groups and depend on the amount of staple food consumed. The bio-fortification strategy seeks to take advantage of the consistent daily consumption of large amounts of food staples by all family members, including women and children who are most at risk for micronutrient malnutrition (CIAT/IFPRI, 2002).

Bio-fortification provides a truly feasible means of reaching malnourished populations in relatively remote rural areas, delivering naturally fortified foods to people with limited access commercially-marketed fortified foods, which are more readily available in urban areas. Nutritionists also agree that bio-fortified crops can improve nutritional status in micronutrient-deficient populations, but additional research is needed, using other, more sensitive biochemical indicators, as well as functional indicators, to more fully understand the health impact of consuming bio-fortified foods (Bouis and Saltzman, 2017)

Bio-fortification and commercial fortification, therefore, are highly complementary. Breeding for higher trace mineral density in seeds will not incur a yield penalty. In fact, bio-fortification may have important spinoff effects for increasing farm productivity in developing countries in an environmentally-beneficial way. Mineral-packed seeds sell themselves to farmers because, as recent research has shown, these trace minerals are essential in helping plants resist disease and other environmental stresses. More seedlings survive and initial growth is more rapid. Ultimately, yields are higher, particularly in trace mineral "deficient" soils in arid regions (CIAT/IFPRI, 2002). Relative to other crops, cassava has several agronomic traits that distinguish it as a food security crop that can be counted on to provide a source of nutrition during crop failures. A meal of typical size meets only 30% of the minimum daily requirement (MDR) for iron and zinc and 10% of the daily pro-vitamin A (β -carotene) requirement. The Nation newspaper (2015) reported that the Country Manager, Harvest Plus Nigeria, Dr Paul Ilona, noted that while the normal cassava provides calories, it does not provide enough micronutrients, such as Vitamin A that are required for good health. These micronutrients are essential as their deficiencies are responsible for some debilitating nutritional disorders, including birth defects, mental and physical retardation, weakened immune systems, blindness and even death. Ilona said people who do not get enough micronutrients suffer from a ‘hidden hunger,’ with serious consequences. Ilona stressed that micronutrients are essential for human health and nutrition. If properly used, it can significantly contribute to reduce morbidity, malnutrition and mortality.

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Conclusion

The way to go in reducing malnutrition among rural and urban household especially among children and women is to foster the consumption of bio-fortified cassava. The study concluded that bio-fortified cassava has the potential to improve the nutrition and health status of rural and urban households which can contribute to household productivity and improve the overall Gross Domestic Products (GDP) of Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study recommends that more awareness on the health and nutritional benefits of bio-fortified cassava should be intensified and all stakeholders in the government and non-governmental organization should be saddled with the responsibility of promoting the consumption of bio-fortified cassava products.

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